

Root Cause Analysis Activity

Transformative Research Unit for Equity
Equity-Centered Transformative Research Tools

Using the Root Cause Analysis Tree in Your Projects

A root cause analysis tree includes three aspects: leaves, trunk, and roots.

Leaves: Symptoms or manifestations of inequitable policies and practices. These are easily seen.

Trunk: Current structures, policies, practices, and cultural systems (norms, values, beliefs, or mental models) that maintain inequitable outcomes

Roots: Historical causes of the problem, which drive policies and practices in the trunk and allow for creation of the leaves. These cannot be easily seen.

Step 1:

Click on this [link](#) to access the jamboard for this activity. You will need to copy the document to work off your personal root cause tree. Start by stating a problem and write it down at the top of the root cause analysis tree. If you are conducting research or evaluation on a specific program or initiative, the problem should align directly with the inequity the program or initiative is aiming to address. If you collect and/or report on data more broadly, think of an inequity that your data may uncover.

Remember, the problem is **NOT** what the program or initiative is doing to try to solve a problem but the actual **problem it is trying to solve**. For example, if you are evaluating a program that aims to increase the number of underrepresented students who graduate with an undergraduate STEM degree by implementing mentoring programs, the problem is NOT “lack of mentoring programs” but the broader problem of “underrepresented students do not graduate with STEM degrees at high rates.” It may be that implementing mentoring programs is ONE strategy to support graduation, but with this activity we are **NOT** interested in how to increase graduation rates (yet), we are interested in understanding **WHY** graduation rates are low.

Step 2:

Start brainstorming reasons for the problem by asking, “What might be contributing to this problem?” Think of current written and unwritten policies, practices, and cultural norms, values, beliefs, or mental models that may be operating in this space. Brainstorm multiple reasons and place it on Jamboard using a yellow sticky note

Policies: Written policies impact decisions or practices. For example, admission requirements impact whether students are even admitted to STEM programs. Unwritten policies develop over time and direct certain practices or workflows. See procedures or workflows or practices for examples.

Procedures or workflows: Workflows refer to actions taken, or processes implemented, based on policies, guidelines, and protocols. An example of a workflow that can affect students’ persistence is inability to secure advising appointments to support their pathway or limited access to financial aid advising.

Practices: Practices include instructional, administrative, and other operations, including training and staff development. An example of a practice could be the categorical placement of multilingual English learners in developmental education classes. This could be based on an explicit policy or an interpretation of a vague policy that leaves placement decisions up to college advisors or staff. Studies have shown that students who are placed in developmental education classes are more likely to get pushed out of college.

Cultural norms, values, beliefs, or mental models: Cultural norms, values, beliefs, or mental models can include stereotypes or biases—both explicit and implicit—that impact how people act in public settings. For example, a mental model of who is a “typical STEM student” may impact how underrepresented students are treated in STEM classes. This may impact their sense of belonging which impacts whether they continue in their classes.

Step 3:

After you have identified current policies and practices, ask why they exist. What historical policies, practices, and/or cultural norms, values, beliefs, or mental models drove the creation of the trunk? These are causes that you are unable to see. Add as many as you can using blue sticky notes. You may not know the history, but do the best you can

Step 4:

Once you have identified some root causes, there may be additional current policies, practices, and/or cultural norms, values, beliefs, or mental models that you may not have thought of initially. Add them to the trunk. Also brainstorm the current policies that keep these conditions in place.

Step 5:

Check to your tree to see if your sticky notes are placed in the accurate category. If you have questions or are unclear with your categorization, that is completely fine! The goal is not to get the right answer but to engage in this process. If you have questions, you can discuss them in the reflection session at the end of the month. One thing to note is to make sure you are not mistaking leaves for the trunk or roots. For example, underrepresented students in STEM may have to work during school. By asking “why” you may write “underrepresented students do not have enough financial aid.” Make sure you drill down deep enough to get at current or historical root causes, such as a system of policies, practices, and/or cultural norms, values, beliefs, or mental models. Don’t stop asking “why” too early, or you may tackle a symptom of the issue rather than the underlying problem.

For example, the three statements below are not “causes” but “symptoms” and result because of inequities in the system:

- “Underrepresented students need to work and can’t fit in enough time for studying.”
- “First-generation college students do not have the support of their families.”
- “Underrepresented students do not have enough financial aid.”

Step 6:

If you are evaluating or researching a program or initiative, reflect on whether it addresses the leaves, trunk, or roots of the tree.